

INFLUENCE OF MARKET ORIENTATION, INNOVATIVE CAPABILITY, NETWORK CAPABILITY AND STRATEGIC AGILITY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF ORGANIZATIONS IN THE INDUSTRIAL GROUP PROCESSED FRUIT BUSINESS IN THAILAND

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Abstract

The popularity of dried fruits is on the rise as health-conscious consumers seek out dietary fiber and iron-rich products. Drying fruit is a value-adding method for Thai fruits, which is accepted abroad. However, Thailand's processed fruit production sector is not keeping up with market demand, resulting in increased production costs and decreased business competitiveness. This research aims to 1) Investigate the level of marketing orientation, innovative ability, networking ability, strategic agility, and organizational performance in the fruit processing industry in Thailand. 2) Study the impact of marketing orientation, innovative ability, networking ability, and strategic agility on the organizational performance of the fruit processing industry in Thailand. 3) Develop a model to determine the organizational performance of the fruit processing industry in Thailand. This study utilized both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The quantitative research involved a sample size of 400 entrepreneurs and executives in the fruit processing industry in Thailand, determined using the criterion of 20 times the observed variable. The data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using structural equation modeling. For the qualitative research, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 processed fruit entrepreneurs and senior executives in the processed fruit business in Thailand. The research results indicate that 1) Thailand's fruit processing industry group has a high level of marketing orientation, innovative ability, networking ability, strategic agility, and organizational performance. 2) Market orientation, innovative capabilities, networking capabilities, and strategic agility significantly affect the organizational performance of the fruit processing industry group in Thailand at the 0.05 level. 3) The researcher has created a model for the organizational performance of the fruit processing industry group called the SMIN-FP Model (S = Strategic Agility, M = Market Orientation, I = Innovative Capabilities, N = Network Capabilities, FP = Firm Performance.) Moreover, qualitative research has identified that Thai entrepreneurs in the fruit processing industry must utilize technology and product innovation to create organizational performance. In doing so, they can develop various styles, flavors, and products that meet international standards and provide the highest customer satisfaction. The findings of this research can be used as a policy to enhance the efficiency and success of the processed fruit industry in Thailand, promoting its growth in the future.

Keywords: Market Orientation / Innovative Capabilities / Network Capabilities / Strategic Agility.

INTRODUCTION

The drive to export goods is crucial for accelerating the export of products to markets that show promising economic expansion and the creation of new markets. It involves monitoring, surveillance, and evaluating the impacts of economic and financial fluctuations globally. It promotes business risk management from exchange rate fluctuations, facilitates convenience, and reduces costs associated with exports. Leveraging the benefits from the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP) framework accompanies monitoring trade barriers to prevent and address problems, particularly non-tariff trade barriers and enhancing export competitiveness. In the first quarter of 2023, the Thai economy expanded by 2.7%, accelerating from 1.4% growth in the previous quarter. Adjusting for seasonal effects, the Thai economy in the first quarter of 2023 expanded from the fourth quarter of 2022 by 1.9% (Office of Economic and Fiscal Policy, 2023).

The Thai economy this year is expected to grow slightly better than last year. Last year, the Thailand Development Research Institute (TDRI) estimated that the Thai economy could expand by 3.2%, while this year's estimate is around 3.5%, slightly higher than last year. The main factors stem from tourism, which is expected to recover significantly. Last year, there were approximately 11 million tourists, and this year, with Chinese tourists included, it could reach 25 million. Therefore, tourism revenue is expected to increase meaningfully, acting as a catalyst for driving Thai economic expansion this year. With increased inflows of money, Thais themselves may see increased incomes, enabling greater spending, thus facilitating Thai economic growth (Stock Exchange of Thailand, 2023).

Although the value of Thailand's fruit exports in the first five months of the year 2023 grew significantly due to being in the crucial fruit delivery season of the year, coupled with the rebound in fresh fruit exports from the low base of the previous year, as well as increased fruit exports to new markets. However, with the slowdown in key trading partner economies, especially China and the United States, along with volatile weather conditions, it may exert pressure on Thailand's fruit export value growth for the remaining period of the year, resulting in Thailand's overall fruit export value for the year 2023 estimated at 7,800 million US dollars, or an expansion of approximately 2.3%. The product groups showing growth trends include fresh, chilled, and frozen fruits due to the expansion of exports to the Chinese market. On the other hand, the product groups showing contraction trends include canned and processed fruits due to reduced orders from key trading partners such as the United States and the European Union (Kasikorn Research Center, 2023).

From the information provided, it is evident that SMEs in Thailand's processed fruit sector have not expanded and grown as much as they should, and they have not responded to market demands adequately. Additionally, SME entrepreneurs must contend with various factors that impact production and overall manufacturing performance in the processed fruit industry. Therefore, researchers are interested in analyzing the current state of production performance in the processed fruit industry among SMEs to provide guidance for promoting enhanced production performance in the processed fruit industry for SMEs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Market orientation is a variable that demonstrates the competitiveness of a business. Entrepreneurs utilize their knowledge and abilities to align their operations with customer needs and market demands (Kurniawan et al., 2020). By incorporating innovation, technology, and integrated marketing strategies, they aim to better access and meet customer expectations, thereby fostering customer confidence and trust in products and businesses capable of gaining competitive advantages from customer loyalty. Marketing practices involve three related aspects: collaboration, group formation, and adapting to competitors. These practices leverage resources gathered by communities through relational networks established and utilized when facing disruptions. Market flexibility fosters new market insights regarding cooperative competitor actions (Hult et al., 2005). Learning motivation and relaxation are crucial in shaping consumers' sustainable attitudes (Gajere et al., 2023).

H1: Marketing focus has a direct positive influence on operational performance.

H5: Marketing focus has a direct positive influence on strategic flexibility.

Innovative capability refers to a business's ability to generate acceptance through the utilization of process concepts. Introducing new products or services is one of the key resources that drives a company's success in the market (Khraim, 2022). Product innovation and management innovation within a company positively affect the organization's operational, financial, and marketing performances (Donkor et al., 2018). The acquisition of new skills and knowledge is a characteristic of innovative capability. Innovative capabilities in service innovation require leveraging existing strategic resources to enhance operations to be adaptable in a rapidly changing environment, fostering growth, gaining a competitive advantage, and impacting service performance. New or improved products, processes, or developments are significantly different from those previously used and ready for implementation (YuSheng & Ibrahim, 2020). The use of technology by organizations assists in managing human resources within the organization, resulting in improved performance (Yildiz & Aykanat, 2021; Wisedsin et al., 2020).

H2: Innovative capability has a positive direct influence on organizational performance.

H6: Innovative capability has a positive direct influence on strategic agility

Networking capability refers to a business's ability to establish business networks, which depends on the unique characteristics of each entrepreneur, as well as the ability to achieve success in network operations. Part of this success comes from the entrepreneurs themselves, who collaborate with other external factors that also point in the same direction, indicating the organization's ability to access resources (Zacca, Dayan & Ahrens, 2015). Strategies for fostering cooperation in network-like forms of innovation or marketing opportunities tend to be pursued by entrepreneurs who see such opportunities, often creating or engaging in networking activities to attain them (Yang & Dooley, 2020; Kerdpitak et al., 2023).

Networking relationships is a domain of individuals, companies, entrepreneurs, and other companies with similar interests. It tends to foster and develop deep data and collaborative new

thinking without being covertly opaque (Garousi et al., 2020). Moreover, it helps facilitate convenient communication, collaboration, data exchange, and internal knowledge dissemination within an organization (Villegas-Puyod et al., 2022). Creating partnerships in international business operations by establishing supportive partnerships enables the sharing of resources across international businesses, multinational businesses, and global-level businesses. Partnering in this sector leads to lower operating costs, fewer errors, and a better understanding of the market due to business partnerships with local businesses in the supply chain. Opening markets provides opportunities for profitability from lower business costs and increased competitiveness (Human & Naudé, 2009).

H3: Networking capability has a positive direct influence on organizational performance.

H7: Networking capability has a positive direct influence on strategic agility.

Strategic agility is the ability to quickly respond to emerging market opportunities. An organization's strategic agility can be defined as its ability to adapt to both external and internal changes, rapidly responding to customer needs and expectations, leading to changes in improving culture, practices, outcomes, and maintaining competitiveness consistently (Ashrafi, Ravasan & Trkman, 2019; Shoham, Rose & Kropp, 2005).

The value of business at various stages of concern, such as big data analysis value, can create organizational agility through knowledge management and impact on processes and competitiveness in the ever-changing world. Customers speedily change their demands, forcing organizations to apply the concept of organizational agility to positively enhance organizational efficiency (Sher & Yang, 2005). Sustainability focus in improving and redefining values by penetrating new markets, using new business models, and introducing new products can reach new customers. Organizations with strategic agility in innovation, creative thinking and quick in market creation increase more returns and profits compared to other competitors in the same market (Doz, 2020; Shin et al., 2015).

H4: Strategic agility has a positive direct influence on organizational performance.

Organizational performance comprises four main components: Financial Perspective, Innovation and Technology, Internal Business Process, and Learning and Growth (Acosta et al., 2018). Evaluating an organization's performance is crucial for modern management, as managers need to be constantly aware of the organization's status and performance to inform strategic decisions and competitive policies, as well as to assess managerial capabilities within the organization.

Additionally, evaluating an organizational performance is vital for determining whether the organization's operations align with its objectives and for setting future directions. According to management theories or concepts, the process or method of evaluating an organizational performance involves comparing the organization's performance against predetermined goals or standards set in advance. Furthermore, it requires providing information or recommendations for improving the organization's operations to align with the established objectives or standards (Clauss et al., 2019).

METHODOLOGY

This research employed an explanatory sequential mixed methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research methodologies. The quantitative research focused on the population of 953 entrepreneurs and managers in the processed fruit business sector in Thailand. The sample consisted of 400 entrepreneurs and managers from this sector, determined based on a proportional ratio of 1 to 20 (20x20). Data collection utilized a multi-stage sampling technique due to constraints in data availability and time. For the quantitative research, researchers used questionnaires as the data collection tool, while for the qualitative research, in-depth interviews were conducted. The data analysis involved Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

RESULTS

The normal distribution of the 18 observed variables studied in the structural equation model (n=400) was examined, using the chi-square test (χ^2). The statistical significance at the .05 level represented non-normally distribution of such variables. On the other hand, if it was found to be not statistically significant (P-value > .50), it revealed normal distribution of such variables, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of observed variables (n=400)

Variable	\bar{X}	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
INTC	4.02	.96	23.88	-3.243	-3.415	22.182	.000
DISS	4.12	.91	22.09	-2.600	-1.544	9.143	.010
CSTF	4.23	.69	16.31	-2.885	-3.756	22.432	.000
MKCL	4.19	.74	17.66	-3.089	-3.525	21.964	.000
PRDI	4.25	.65	15.29	-2.624	-2.416	12.722	.002
PROI	4.23	.65	15.37	-2.500	-2.355	11.797	.003
MRKI	4.26	.69	16.20	-3.248	-2.770	18.223	.000
MNGI	4.10	.78	19.02	-2.638	-1.529	9.299	.010
SHKW	4.05	.90	22.22	-2.668	-3.213	17.445	.000
NTWC	4.01	.92	22.94	-2.629	-2.442	12.874	.002
CMRJ	4.06	.90	22.17	-3.204	-2.970	19.086	.000
INTD	3.88	.95	24.48	-2.132	-2.139	9.120	.010
REPS	4.11	.64	15.57	-1.542	-.101	2.388	.303
PFMC	4.14	.67	16.18	-1.800	-2.148	7.854	.020
FLXB	4.03	.72	17.87	-1.827	-.803	3.980	.137
QUCK	4.08	.68	16.67	-1.774	-.980	4.108	.128
FINC	4.04	.67	16.58	-1.399	-.990	2.938	.230
IVTC	4.15	.70	16.87	-2.335	-2.681	12.640	.002
ITPC	4.17	.59	14.15	-1.219	.326	1.593	.451
LRDV	4.21	.65	15.44	-2.698	-2.521	13.631	.001

Note: chi-square (χ^2) with statistical significance (P-value <.05) indicates a non-normal distribution

The researchers have checked the quality of the variables studied in the model by testing construct validity of each latent variable using the Confirm Factor Analysis technique by considering the greater than .30 standardized factor loadings to confirm a good observed

variable. It was considered from the R² to check reliability of the empirical variables as well as directly examining the Construct Reliability ($\rho_c > .60$) of the latent variables and Average Variable Extracted ($\rho_v > 0.50$), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Factor loadings (n = 400)

Variables	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	T	R ²
Market orientation)OREM)				
Intellectual creation (INTC)	.50	.25	9.32	.75
Dissemination of intelligence (DISS)	.48	.26	9.27	.74
Customer focus (CSTF)	.88	.22	15.44	.78
Marketing culture (MKCL)	.76	.23	13.67	.77
Innovative capability)INVCP)				
Product innovation (PRDI)	.84	.29	19.67	.71
Process innovation (PROI)	.82	.34	18.83	.66
Marketing innovation (MRKI)	.86	.26	20.33	.74
Management innovation (MNGI)	.44	.81	8.74	.19
Networking capability)NWCP)				
Sharing knowledge (SHKW)	.82	.32	19.57	.68
Networking organization culture (NTWC)	.91	.18	22.92	.82
Combining relationship capital with joint power (CMRJ)	.90	.19	22.61	.81
Independence (INTD)	.83	.31	19.75	.69
Strategic agility)STGAG)				
Responsiveness (REPS)	.81	.35	17.77	.65
Performance (PFMC)	.79	.38	17.34	.62
Flexibility (FLXB)	.46	.79	9.03	.21
Quick (QUCK)	.79	.37	17.37	.63
Organizational performance)OGPRM)				
Finance (FINC)	.86	.26	18.66	.74
Innovation and technology (IVTC)	.75	.43	16.05	.57
Internal process (ITPC)	.71	.50	14.74	.50
Learning and development (LRDV)	.68	.54	14.00	.46
$\rho_c = .84$ $\rho_v = .57$				
Chi-Square=0.01, df=1, P-value=0.91172, RMSEA=0.000				

Table 3: Direct effect, indirect effect, and total effect)n=400(

Dependent variables	R ²	Effect	Independent variables			
			Strategic agility)STGAG)	Market orientation)OREM)	Innovative capability)INVCP)	Networking capability)NWCP)
Strategic agility)STGAG)	.84	DE	-	.54*(5.13)	.86*(10.56)	.64*(10.55)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.54*(5.13)	.86*(10.56)	.64*(10.55)
Organizational performance)OGPRM)	.96	DE	.64*(6.91)	.58*(8.43)	.61*(5.50)	.32*(7.41)
		IE	-	.35*(6.13)	.31*(4.68)	.49*(6.66)
		TE	.64*(6.91)	.93*(7.41)	.92*(10.56)	.81*(8.48)

$\chi^2 = 253.16$ df = 138 p-value = .00000, $\chi^2 / df = 1.83$, RMSEA = .047, RMR = .038, SRMR = .041, CFI = .97, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 223.11

*statistical significance at the .05 level

Note: In parentheses, they were the t-value. If the value was not between -1.96 and 1.96, it was statistically significant at the .05 level. DE=Direct Effect, IE=Indirect Effect, TE=Total Effect

Figure 1: Adjusted structural equation model (n=400)

The results of the data analysis indicated that the model was fit with the observational data by allowing the variance of standard errors (θ) of the 22 pairs of observed variables to have a relationship, with degrees of freedom (df) before adjustment being 160 and df after adjustment being 138, it was found that the adjusted model fitted well with the observational data. This conclusion was based on fit indices as follows: $\chi^2 = 253.16$, $df = 138$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.83$, $RMSEA = .047$, $RMR = .038$, $SRMR = .041$, $CFI = .97$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 223.11$, as shown in Table 3 and Figure 1.

The results of the goodness-of-fit index revealed that $\chi^2 = 253.16$, $df = 138$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, not meeting the statistical significance criterion ($P\text{-value} > .05$). However, the χ^2 was sensitive to sample size. The χ^2/df of $1.83 < 2.00$ within an acceptable range was considered. Other acceptable fit indices are as follows: $RMSEA = .047 < .05$, $RMR = .038 < .05$, $SRMR = .041 < .05$, $CFI = 1.00 > .97$, $GFI = .94 > .90$, $AGFI = .91 > .90$, and $CN = 223.11 > 200.00$. Based on these goodness-of-fit indices, it concluded that the adjusted structural equation model fitted well with the observational data. The parameter estimates in the model were considered acceptable.

CONCLUSION

The results found that the adjusted structural equation model of Influences of Market Orientation, Innovative Capability, Network Capability and Strategic Agility on the Performance of Organizations in the Industrial Group Processed Fruit Business in Thailand was fit with the empirical data at an acceptable level, which was considered from the fit Indexes as follows: $\chi^2 = 253.16$, $df = 138$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.83$, $RMSEA = .047$, $RMR = .038$, $SRMR = .041$, $CFI = .97$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 223.11$. The model's estimates are presented as follows:

- 1) Market Orientation (OREM) has a direct influence on Organizational Performance (OGPRM) with an effect coefficient of $.58^*(8.43)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 1, market orientation has a direct influence on organizational performance, is supported.
- 2) Innovative Capability (INVCP) has a direct influence on Organizational Performance (OGPRM) with an effect coefficient of $.61^*(5.50)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 2, innovative capability has a direct influence on organizational performance, is supported.
- 3) Networking Capability (NWCP) has a direct influence on Organizational Performance (OGPRM) with an effect coefficient of $.32^*(7.41)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 3, networking capability has a direct influence on organizational performance, is supported.
- 4) Strategic Agility (STGAG) has a direct influence on Organizational Performance (OGPRM) with an effect coefficient of $.64^*(6.91)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 4, strategic agility has a direct influence on organizational performance, is supported.
- 5) Market Orientation (OREM) has a direct influence on Strategic Agility (STGAG) with an effect coefficient of $.54^*(5.13)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 5, market orientation has a direct influence on strategic agility, is supported.
- 6) Innovative Capability (INVCP) has a direct influence on strategic agility (STGAG) with an effect coefficient of $.86^*(10.56)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 6, innovative capability has a direct influence on strategic agility, is supported.
- 7) Networking Capability (NWCP) has a direct influence on Strategic Agility (STGAG) with an effect coefficient of $.64^*(10.55)$ and statistical significance at the .05 level. As a result, hypothesis 7, networking capability has a direct influence on strategic agility, is supported.
- 8) Market Orientation (OREM), Innovative Capability (INVCP), Networking Capability (NWCP) and Strategic Agility (STGAG) can together predict Organizational Performance (OGPRM) by 96%.
- 9) Market Orientation (OREM), Innovative Capability (INVCP) and Networking Capability (NWCP) can together predict Strategic Agility (STGAG) by 84%

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